

The South African Police Service in South Africa Fails to Nurture Talent Development

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Abstract:- The article investigates the problems faced by the South African Police Service regarding the acute shortage and development of talent and why talent management has been not been introduced in the Police Department. It examines the importance and benefits of developing talent management programmes at the Police Department and demonstrates why the police needs talent management to develop future leaders. It also seeks to find out whether the Police are ready to implement a TM programme. The importance of developing talent management programmes in the police service to develop and build a talent pool as a key human resource. Secondly, discuss factor(s) that cause(s) the poor implementation of talent management practices within the police. Lastly, examine how the employees perceive the influence of better talent management practices in the police. It assesses the relevance of talent management and makes recommendations on how to develop an integrated talent management programme, to achieve the mission objectives of the government. It seeks to find out the challenges and obstacles that hinder the development of talent management within the South African Police Service Department in South Africa. The following factors are also discussed. This research article will contribute to the literature on talent management practice and its influence on the sustainability of organisational routine in the South African Police Service in South Africa. This article offers a holistic approach to using and managing human potential most efficiently and practically through talent management, notwithstanding the numerous problems and institutional resource constraints. The findings of the article have practical implications as they help raise awareness amongst the decision makers within the police service of the need for developing talent management capabilities. They will also make a valuable contribution to knowledge through reviewing and expanding the literature on talent management programmes, and provide an opportunity for researchers to undertake further studies which could be useful for different organisations wishing to develop talent management programmes.

Keywords:- Talent management, Police officials, Training and development, Employees Turnover, Talent management strategies, Talent Management programmes.

I. INTRODUCTION AND BACKGROUND

Organisations recognise that talent management (TM) is important in ensuring a competitive advantage (Collings and Mellahi, 2009; Fegley, 2006a; Gallardo-Gallardo, Dries and González-Cruz, 2013; Goetsch, 2010; Khoreva, Vaiman and Van Zalk, 2017; McDonnell, Collings, Mellahi and Schuler, 2017; Vaiman, Scullion and Collings, 2012), however, they lament their TM efforts fail (Ashton and Morton, 2005; Beechler and Woodward, 2009; Bersin, Houston and Kester, 2014; Collings, 2014, 2015). Several reasons are advanced for the ineffective TM efforts, ranging from skills shortages and the ‘war for talent’ (Frank, Finnegan and Taylor, 2004; Ewerlin, 2013; Hejase, Hejase, Mikdashi and Bazeih, 2016; Nilsson and Ellström, 2012; Vaiman et al. 2012). Talent management is a strategic, integrated approach to managing the career of an employee, from the moment of attraction to the institution (recruitment), through selecting the suitable candidate for a position, employing the various phases of developing an employee, through the continuous motivation of an employee towards performance and actions to retain the employee (Vermeulen, 2008:40).

Davies and Davies (2010:419) underscore Vermeulen’s definition that talent management is the systematic attraction, identification, development, engagement, retention and deployment of employees to the best of their abilities and capacities. Therefore, talent management is a continuous process throughout an employee’s career; integrated with various Human Resource Management (HRM) practices. In this study, the focus is on managing talented tutors/trainers (hereafter referred to as academics) in the South African Police Service (hereafter referred to as SAPS), with significant potential and of particular value to the institution.

II. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK: INTEGRATED TALENT MANAGEMENT FRAMEWORK

The integrated Talent Management conceptual framework, according to Amala and Aarulandu (2021), displays the framework and resources required to recruit, use, develop and retain the top talent in each profession. This will aid organisations in making workforce-wide, smarter, quicker, data-driven decisions. HR and the manager collaborate throughout the talent management continuum to manage the employee experience from hire to retirement or transition. The researcher’s model, which was built on the

talent management aspects with additional chosen factors, can be adapted for use in public sector organisations (Kumar & Rajasekar, 2013).

Fig 1 Integrated Talent Management Framework

Retrieved from: [https:// www.valamis.com/hub/talent-management#talent-management](https://www.valamis.com/hub/talent-management#talent-management)

The Integrated Talent Management model will be discussed below:

➤ *Talent Strategy And Planning:*

In its broadest sense, talent planning is a set of people management tactics used by businesses to recruit and keep outstanding talent (Thunnissen & Buttiens, 2017). These procedures, which aim to develop and preserve a high-performing workforce, are regularly modified to meet the demands and overarching goals of the particular organisation. However, creating risk-reduction strategies and company plans requires planning. This process will assist the employer to have the right people in the right roles to satisfy the expectations of the organisation; for this to play out the organisation must, of course, have a talent planning strategy in place (Thunnissen & Buttiens, 2017). Given how frequently organisational requirements change, it is essential to keep the personnel planning strategy closely aligned with the current business objectives (Thunnissen & Gallardo Gallardo, 2004).

➤ *Talent Acquisition:*

The process of hiring talent has been well-defined as talent acquisition (Stahl et al., 2012), and using a long-term strategy for hiring that is in line with the organisational objective (Hongal & Kinange, 2020) is important for each institution. This process assists with identifying, attracting, engaging, and retaining highly qualified personnel and provides the foundation for the organisation's current

competencies which will help with its future business needs (Hongal & Kinange, 2020). Many organisations discriminate between the benefits of utilizing modern talent acquisition technology and the chance to rationalize the entire recruitment process (Hongal & Kinange, 2020). The development of employee value applications and manager adjustments are increasingly prioritized in these talent management methods to retain and cultivate the best personnel for the positions (Martin & Sinclair, 2019).

➤ *Talent Performance Management:*

When implementing strategic goals, talent management and performance management are used as tactical methods to enhance employee and organisational performance (Masri and Suliman, 2019). Organisations are urged to develop a talent culture that will allow staff members to support strategic goals and maintain talent performance stability (Masale, 2020): in essence, clear roles, opportunities to utilize talents and participation in career decisions are all necessary for talented employees to flourish professionally (Lesenyeh, 2017). Furthermore, compensation, work-life balance, leadership and management support, performance management and growth and occupational health and safety are all important elements of talent management in the public sector (Alves et al., 2020).

➤ *Talent Development:*

The strategic direction of the organisation must be connected to talent development, which is a crucial component of the talent management process (Lesenyeh, 2017). It is believed that the employee will be happier and more fulfilled when the talent development goals, including transparent information, leadership development programmes, mentorship and succession planning, benefit the demands of both workers and organisations (Bidwell, 2018). Given the rapidly changing environment, developing talent is a critical responsibility for public sector organisations (Boselie & Thunnissen, 2017). The talent resources of an organisation can be strengthened at all levels of the organisation, according to experts, through informal training, employee development, and communication frameworks. An organisation will be viewed favourably if it displays a desire to help its people grow (Saurombe et al., 2017): consider, for example, the (numerous) encounters between a public worker and the general population. The soft talents that employers frequently seek out include resilience, flexibility, empathy, responsibility, communication skills, decision-making, teamwork, attitude, time management, critical thinking, and interpersonal skills.

➤ *Succession Planning:*

In succession planning, there are various points of view, but they all have a similar basis. Although some regard succession planning as simply a process for choosing the next leadership team (Siambi, 2022), the management activity of succession planning, which focuses on personnel planning, actually comprises locating, attracting, and developing candidates for leadership and managing positions (Javis, 2019). Building a talent pool, succession planning and management are all viewed as continuing strategic tasks for a corporation to ensure that the company's mission is carried out in the case of changes in leadership and/or in the workforce (OHCS, 2022). An organisation must plan for succession management, with replacement planning being less important than predicting future organisational demands (Siambi, 2022). Leadership succession planning confirms that keeping the current workforce is one of the most important issues businesses face today. This is due to the impact that succession planning has on organisational performance (Siambi, 2022). An employee is impacted by effective succession planning in a variety of ways including employee career development, compensation management, and retention rate (Javis, 2019). The focus should be on career management and talent management as part of the succession planning framework, which should be adopted to retain staff (Obianuju et al., 2021). Promotions of talented individuals should be deliberate decisions since succession planning should always result in employee retention.

➤ *Leadership Development:*

Effective planning, efficiency, transparency, and accountability are all essential components of excellent public government (Moldoveanu & Narayandas, 2019). Due to its focus on identifying and retaining high-potential people, talent management is typically perceived as a component of talent development in the public sector. It

might involve retraining and upskilling personnel in addition to other focused programs to get them ready for career growth. Talent development refers to efforts to find, nurture, and elevate employees inside an organisation. Talent is recognized as a crucial component of both local and global talent management (Alferaih et al., 2018). Organisations transform the talent they already have into the leaders they will need in the future through leadership development (Dalayga and Baskaran, 2019). To encourage the growth of outstanding performances in certain occupational domains, such as business, the visual and performing arts, health and education, technology, social behavioral sciences, and others, talent development involves the utilization of specific resources (Javis, 2019). Talent must be developed with the appropriate instruction and growth to cultivate the required aptitude and capabilities (Li et al., 2018). The leadership development sector, however, is in disarray. The number of individuals providing training in the hard and soft skills needed by corporate managers has increased (Moldoveanu & Narayandas, 2019), but regrettably, talent is not necessarily retained.

➤ *Talent Compensation:*

Talent compensation, according to research, is quickly evolving in terms of both compensation and benefits (Barkhuizen & Gumede, 2022). To keep those vital, talented individuals in the company, compensation is a crucial factor (Barkhuizen & Gumede, 2022). Promotion is less significant than the importance of bonuses and incentive programmes that managers have for the workforce. The ability to pay well is crucial for luring and keeping talented people. According to Holland and Scullion, (2019) attracting top personnel requires a compensation plan that includes high salary, perks, and variable pay. Motivation is necessary to keep employees on board since rewards other than a competitive compensation package may tempt them not to perform or to look for employment opportunities elsewhere (Lazear, 2018). A company must provide a competitive wage package to keep good personnel. The interaction between a situation and a person produces motivation. All parties, including unions and politicians, engage in collective bargaining to determine wage and employee benefit programs in the public sector (Barkhuizen & Gumede, 2022).

➤ *Employee Branding Strategy*

Employee branding is defined as a worker's impact on a company's branding through their diligent work to create long-term brand value (Chandrasekaran, 2020). Employee branding can also be thought of as the concept of a collection of financial, practical, and psychological benefits that an organisation offers to its employees to create a clear management model to achieve the highest priority goals while boosting productivity that will advance the hiring process, foster greater employee loyalty, and lower the turnover rate (Alves et al., 2020). Talent management strategies like fair rewards and remuneration are the finest markers of an engaging business brand (Maura and Agarwal, 2018).

➤ *Talent Retention Practices*

One of the key goals of good talent management systems is employee talent retention, which is dependent on management, employment equity, equal opportunity, and managers' influence (Holland & Scullion, 2019). Along with other factors affecting job satisfaction and employee retention, talent management must be taken into consideration. Effective retention strategies typically start with good hires leaving an organisation, but it is still unclear how companies keep their staff members (Pate & Scullion, 2018). Retention becomes more difficult due to increased mobility, remote working opportunities, the lack of long-term employment ties, and conventional psychological agreements (Scullion et al., 2020). Changing your talents might be expensive (Holland & Scullion, 2022).

➤ *Talent Management Assistance for Employees:*

Talent management is essential to current industries and is regarded as one of the central administration functions in the workplace. Rinaldhy (2021) cited the following main reimbursements that talent management can offer:

- Fulfilling the workplace dream with the assistance of effective and gifted individuals,
- Assisting the organisation with a pool of gifted individuals to encounter imminent needs,
- Making the workplace more modest yet advanced,
- Paving the techniques for future leadership,
- Improving onboarding experience,
- Career advancement and providing more opportunities for improved skills.
- Such benefits make employees feel wanted and that experience leads the organisation to have improved performance in reaching their goals.

➤ *The measure of the Aspects and talent management:*

Most South African-based quantitative research methodologies were located in Municipalities as opposed to the public sector (Tarique, 2021). The scant information the researcher could obtain by combing existing databases exposed the lack in the South African public sector in particular of systematic literature and empirical studies on talent management. Specifically, the practice has not been grounded in management theory (Tetik, 2017), nor has it been evaluated or analyzed as a full system, leaving several unresolved concerns. This implies that talent management as an area of study is underdeveloped in the public sector, with researchers claiming a lack of theory and breadth (Shabana, 2017).

III. TALENT MANAGEMENT

It appears that there is not a consistent definition of what talent management is globally, and even in South Africa. Talent management plays a vital role in achieving organisational excellence (Shashi. et al., 2020). Talent management or human capital management is a set of business practices that manage the planning, acquisition, development, retention and growth of talent so that the organization can achieve business goals by optimizing

performance. Talent management enables an organisation to meet its needs for flexibility, competitiveness, and efficiency (Luna-Arocas & Morley, 2017). In most cases, talent management helps guarantee that employees optimize their talents for the organisation's success (Mahfoozi et al., 2018). The concept of talent management can be traced back to a classical work by Kelly (1963) entitled "The Limit" in which they demonstrated how talent management was noted as the source of a bright future. Since then, public and commercial sectors have made talent management central to making sure that they acquire, advance, and retain the best-talented workforces. The concept of talent management focuses on specifying the kind of skills required, building a diverse candidate pool, retention of employees, encouraging research and development, recruiting, and succession planning (Anlesinya et al., 2019).

Talent management practices depend on the organisational capacity and culture leading to a variation in the implementation (Kravariti, 2022). Finding talented individuals is a challenge and is one of the decade's key managerial concerns (Mtshali et al., 2018). Public sector organisations face an increasing talent war, and some agonize over a chronic personnel deficit (Ogbari et al., 2018). However, public sector organisations' approaches to talent management are resolute in terms of how they define talent and how well they implement it (Gallardo-Gallardo et al., 2020). Talent management assumes attracting, developing and retaining a required talented workforce in a way that promotes gender equality. Ensuring the balanced representation of female and male personnel is essential for police services to be able to prevent, detect and investigate crimes against women and men effectively.

The mainstream talent management publications focus on talent management in private sector companies and multinational corporations (Gallardo-Gallardo et al., 2020), despite the rising interest in talent management in the theoretical literature over the past period (Glaster et al., 2019, Gallardo-Gallardo et al., 2020).

Talent management within the public sector provides an interesting topic to be studied especially in the South African continent. According to Shabana (2017), the public sector background is complex because institutional mechanisms have a substantial impact. This indicates that the organisational context must be considered when researching talent management in the public sector. Some studies on talent management have ignored contextual factors in the development of work relationships and human resource management (Mahfoozi et al., 2018). Several authors call for more research in various sectors and industries (Al Jawali et al., 2021, Anlesinya et al., 2019). According to Shabana (2017), the number of research papers on talent management has increased over the last decade (Filippus and Schultz, 2019). However, little theoretical growth in the field had been observed, other than challenges around the concept's definition (Shabana, 2017).

Consequently, even though private sector business and consultancy firms have made talent management a strategic priority, there seems to be a need for an academic contribution to the theoretical frameworks within a South African public sector perspective. Furthermore, it appears that there is no connection between talent management practices and the public sector's overall organisational performance (Boselie et al., 2021), and there is also a lack of succession planning, skills assessments, or organisational cultures that support talent management (Kaleem, 2019). Tariq et al., (2013) assert that South African public service departments struggle to retain qualified workers because the workers leave for better-paying private sector corporate organisations. Mtshali et al. (2018) state that the South African public sector continues to lose informed, capable and experienced individuals, as well as senior managers with relevant expertise in important positions. There has been a significant staff turnover at the level of senior managers including director generals over the past decade (Shabana, 2017; Shava and Doorgapersad, 2021). This has had a substantial impact on service delivery as institutional memory is lost, resulting in service delivery failure. However, there hasn't been much research conducted on the methods of personnel administration used in the South African public sector.

Talent management is an input-output process: it involves activities such as attracting, onboarding, engaging, developing, and retaining talent (Thunnissen, Boselie & Fruytier, 2013). Talent management is one of the most important aspects in any organisation, and it is that talent that may assist a company to thrive. As a strategic business partner, the human resources department must prioritise employee experience through talent management. It is something that can make a huge difference about retention, employee performance, value added to work and commitment (Kimani, Kara & Njagi, 2013).

IV. HISTORICAL OVERVIEW OF TALENT DEVELOPMENT

The introduction of the concept of talent management is usually linked to McKinsey's Report "The War for Talent" published in 1998. Since then, the concept of TM has gained huge popularity among scholars and practitioners (Lewis & Heckman 2006; Cappelli, 2008; Iles Chuai, & Preece, 2010; Collings & Mellahi 2009; Shen & Hall, 2009; Farndale, Scullion & Sparrow, 2010; Caplan, 2010; Joyce & Slocum, 2012; Stahl, Bjorkman, & Farndale, 2012; Al Ariss, Cascio & Paauwe, 2014; Claussen Grohsjean, Luger, & Probst, 2014). Managing talents assumes 'an organization's efforts to systematically attract, identify, develop, and retain skilled and valuable employees – talents', either because of their 'high potential' for the future or because they are fulfilling business/operation critical roles" (Campbell & Smith, 2010:2). As such, talent management is concerned with all the HRM processes, with a precise focus on the attraction, development and retention of talents (Lewis & Heckman, 2006).

However, in the relevant literature, different perceptions and insights into talent management can be found. According to Iles et al. (2010) and Capelli (2008), there are at least three different ways of understanding talent management. Firstly, some authors are viewing it as a rebranding term of HRM with a strategic focus on all HRM activities. Secondly, talent management is often understood as focused only on talented people - a talent pool, both internally and externally to the organization, by using HRM instruments. Finally, talent management may be viewed as focused on talent flows - management of talent progression within an organization rather than on the talent pool. Talent management has been perceived as part of human resource management strategies, where it consists of the implementation of integrated strategies that are executed to improve and sustain the organizational performance by improving procedures for attracting, retaining, developing, and profiting from individuals with the necessary qualifications and skills to achieve present and future business requirements (Cheese, Thomas, & Craig, 2007). Talent is a superpower with the ability to accomplish much or act in physical, mental, legal, moral, and financial ways (Bhambani and Sanii, 2017). Bhambani and Sanii (2017) describe the challenge that organisations face today as they compete to find and keep outstanding individuals. The act, method, or practice of managing, handling, supervising, and controlling, personnel to achieve organisational goals is referred to as management. As implied by the term talent management, the idea goes beyond simply selecting the best candidates at the right moment, but includes discovering each person's unique and outstanding traits as well as fostering and developing those qualities to produce the unique desired results for that institution. Furthermore, according to Bhambani and Sanii (2017), while hiring the best talent available for the organisation at the right time may be a major source of worry, keeping that talent producing optimally while transitioning them into the organisation's culture and further maximizing their potential, is an even bigger worry. An organisation that understands the notion of talent management well is likely to have an advantage over competitors.

➤ Importance and benefits of talent management:

Talent management plays a crucial factor in many organisations in the hiring and retaining of key employees as well as having a degree of commitment among the staff (Rinaldhy, 2021). Talent management helps organisations to change the future of the business by connecting human resources and management initiatives (Hongal and Kinange, 2020). Furthermore, talent management supports the workforce, enabling workers to identify their strengths and tailor their output to the establishment's corporate identity, which will boost client satisfaction and business performance will increase as a result (Hongal and Kinange, 2020).

Talent management has a significant role to play in organisations in the first decade of the twenty-first century, and employers are increasingly becoming aware of how the employment relationship is evolving. The advanced economies' product base is transitioning from an industrial

one to a service-based one with a knowledge focus. The current trends i.e. worldwide abundance, but the local shortage of talent, have presented challenges to businesses.

➤ *The following tendencies are the most widely discussed, according to Collings and Gallardo-Gallardo (2021):*

- There aren't many young people in corporate work and many of the older employees are fast approaching retirement. Depending on the national demographic background, the order will change.
- Additional generational differences and parallels are observed in the workplace.
- The workforce is more diversified, remote and virtual than before and contains many different attitudes to work.
- New working practices and new partnerships between customers and suppliers are evolving.

➤ *Talent management benefits are the following for an organization:*

- Talent is able to shape and enhance organizational value and performance
- Talent is scarce, incomparable and unique
- Talent is able to create and sustain competitive advantage,
- Talent has innovative and creative potential,

- Talent is a combination of knowledge, skills, and abilities necessary for the business,
- The war for talent affects developed and developing countries. In advanced countries, the shortage of talent is made worse by a shift in demographics whereby the aging population is on the rise and the number of young people is on the decline.

Brewster and Cerdin (2014) point out that all organisations have a system for talent management whether by design or default. Talent management can be linked to the initiatives of talent management and how they ensure the success of organisations. According to Massie (2015), talent identification and development in organizations continues to be a significant strategic tool for organizations that want to remain competitive. Massie (2015) argues that the main objective of talent management is to optimise the performance of the organization by creating a sustainable and high-performing organization capable of meeting its strategic objectives and enjoying a competitive advantage over its competitors (see also Kaur, 2013). Brunila and Yneller (2013) found that talent management practices that are centred on the organizational strategy have a substantially greater effect on promoting the company brand whilst providing satisfactory client service. Companies with an attractive company brand become more attractive to the employees who regard them as the employer of choice as more talented employees want to be associated with such organizations. These initiatives are illustrated in the figure below.

Fig 2 Talent Management Initiatives

Source: <https://lurnii.com/blog/what-is-talent-management-and-why-is-it-important>

➤ *Talent Management Theories:*

Attracting and keeping employees has become a key component of contemporary human resources management. Several established ideas, including the resource-based view (RBV), the human capital theory (HCT), and the institutional theory (IT), are the foundation of talent

management (Gallardo-Gallardo et al., 2020). While HCT emphasizes the need for organisations to capitalize on people who can be loyal to a single organisation or more universal, the RBV summarises how talent management practices can be associated with the business approach to reach maintainable benefits (Sarabi, 2019).

The HCT is the first theory to establish a link between increased productivity, ongoing competitive advantage, and investments in an organisation's most valuable resource, its people. According to institutional theory, organisations are under social pressure to adopt strategies and practices that are compatible with their institutional environment (Shashi et al., 2020) and to adhere to the laws, ordinances, and value systems set out by that environment. As a result, the IT

perception also clarifies the alterations in personnel management strategies amongst small, medium-sized, and big organisations (Savarimuthu & Joth, 2018). Notwithstanding this work, the current difficulty has been the lack of study into HR administration, which has had an effect on talent management practices in the public sector and has left a significant breach in our thinking of how the HR role frames the essential issues in talent management.

➤ *Talent Management Process Model*

Fig 3 Talent Management Process Model

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The talent management process model in Figure 2 above includes the following elements: success planning, performance management, employee planning, talent acquisition, career development, and employee compensation, all of which are typically discussed by researchers. The employee branding strategy is typically left out of these discussions. The study will provide in-depth information about a framework for talent management that consists of the number of parts divided into categories like branding strategy, talent strategy, planning, talent acquisition, select talent, employee performance management, training and development, succession planning identifying, and total rewards. The framework that will be discussed is called Integrated talent management.

- To devise a strategy for talent management as an employee engagement strategy for transparent and open communication.
- To develop and implement more employee recognition programmes for top performers in consultation with employees and leadership.
- To develop tailor-made leadership development programmes because Pension Funds are a highly specialised industry.
- The police should conduct a Skills Audit to determine whether there is a critical skills gap.
- The police to appoint change agents, champions and ambassadors made up of departmental management and leadership who will be responsible for talent pooling, talent development and retention through recognition, job rotation, on-the-job training, e-learning programmes, work-related tutorials, educational courses, and internships.
- The future development of a talent management strategy needs to be holistic including the diverse needs of the police. One of the key challenges when trying to implement a talent management strategy in the police is translating complex and vague talent management theories and approaches from the literature into a strategy that has practical implications and is suitable within the police organisational culture.

V. RECOMMENDATIONS WITH PRACTICAL IMPLEMENTATION

- Talent is becoming a rare commodity in the Police Department, so it must be treated shrewdly to get the best possible results. At the moment a clear talent management strategy is missing in the SAPS. Several gaps and flaws exist in the organisation regarding mechanisms for identifying, attracting, developing, and retaining talent.

- Implementing a TM strategy is not forcing a fit, but requires a fine balance of cultural tolerance, processes, an adequate organisational structure and good management support.
- TM strategy requires making appropriate investments (select, train, develop, reward) and winning the war for talent means primarily focusing on retaining existing staff.
- Building loyalty and commitment through engagement or participation in decision-making is the way forward for the police to generate sustainable competitive advantage in achieving the SA Government 2030 Vision. In addition, The police need to introduce an appraisal system of the current police positions in terms of talent capabilities to identify, attract, develop, and retain the talent within the organisation.
- Organisational culture needs to change to motivate employees by offering transparent promotion opportunities for all. This would require setting up and standardising inclusive rather than exclusive (personal development and performance review) through developing clear job descriptions, so that the skills, abilities and experience needed from a new employee are identified.
- A Talent Management department needs to be set up and a task force appointed to design and implement a homemade TM strategy, by periodically headhunting and recruiting employees with promising potential and who fit in with the police culture.
- Law enforcement institutions can capitalise on the benefits of more contemporary performance management systems to track, enhance and sustain the performance of police officials. There was some evidence of training and development opportunities and talent onboarding practices for police officials.
- The research results also showed that more attention should be paid to officials' performance management. Talent management and performance management are synonymous.
- Continuous career and professional development are essential for police officials to fulfill their duties and delivery quality and reliable service to the public.

VI. CONCLUSION

The Police has now begun to recognize the importance of human resources within the workplace and has expressed unease with regard to this. This unease has been acknowledged despite the Police proving its value and being determined to preserve security and constancy in trying to ensure that all human and monetary competencies are set in place in order to achieve its vision. Contained within the strategy of the Police, the campaign to promote familiarity with the perception of developing Talent Management among police sector employees, and indeed employees at all departmental levels, has developed into an area of greater interest and need for this article.

This article provided useful insights into the talent management practice for police officials. The results highlight the importance of efficient talent management

practice to prevent voluntary turnover of police officials. Furthermore, the results of the article also emphasize the need to pay more attention to the talent management of different generations to ensure a sustainable workforce. This article also requires policing leaders to realise the critical role that they play in fostering a conducive work environment for police officials. A healthy work climate will translate itself into the service performance required from police officials to maintain law and order.

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